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A legal analysis of the reuse of aquaculture effluents, fish processing waste, and algae biomass

LAND-BASED rearing of marine Pearl Oysters in India

Mediterranean Marine Finfish Aquaculture Demonstration Centre (MMF-ADC)

HALOPHYTES BIOREFINERY AND FUNCTIONAL FEEDS

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Salicornia ramosissima as a high-value source of bioactives for shrimp and fish feeds

Salicornia ramosissima, a salt-tolerant halophyte, is a sustainable source of bioactive compounds with applications in animal nutrition, particularly aquaculture. Due to its ability to thrive in saline environments and on marginal land, this plant presents a promising opportunity to produce valuable extracts without competing with traditional crops. Such characteristics are specifically relevant given that the intensification of aquaculture practices is associated with challenges related to stress, bacterial diseases and welfare. In this context, the inclusion of bioactives from *S. ramosissima* in functional feeds for farmed aquatic animals emerges as a promising solution.

The potential of including *Salicornia* co-products in fish and shrimp diets has been previously confirmed in the project AQUACOMBINE, highlighting their value not only as a sustainable carbohydrate source, helping to decrease dependence on edible cereal crops like wheat, but also as a functional ingredient that improves animal health. In European seabass, *Salicornia* dietary inclusion has been shown to enhance antioxidant status and regulate inflammatory responses. Similarly, in shrimp it has demonstrated the ability to strengthen immune function and increase resistance to *Vibrio parahaemolyticus* infection. These positive effects are believed to originate from *Salicornia*'s rich phytochemical makeup, which includes hydroxycinnamic acids, fatty acids, terpenoids, flavonoids, alkaloids, steroids, tannins, saponins, quinones, and coumarins, many of which are recognized for their therapeutic properties in humans. Building on these promising results, IGNITION aims to develop optimal extraction methods of bioactive compounds from *S. ramosissima* and evaluate their potential to improve the performance, health and disease resistance of aquatic animals, using both *in vitro* and *in vivo* approaches.

Fine-tuning Salicornia ramosissima potential: Extraction and characterization of bioactives

As part of the IGNITION project, extensive research has been carried out by Aalborg University (AAU) and Halorefine A/S, Denmark to further explore the potential of *Salicornia ramosissima*. The goal is not only to identify and quantify these beneficial compounds but

also to improve the methods used to extract them, ensuring maximum recovery in an environmentally friendly and scalable way.

S. ramosissima was selected for this in-depth study due to its high availability and impressive phytochemical profile. From a compositional standpoint, both the juice and fibre components of the plant are rich in nutrients. The juice contains a significant amount of sugars, proteins, and naturally occurring salts, while the fibrous residue is high in carbohydrates, making it suitable for biorefining applications. However, the real value lies in the secondary metabolites found within the plant's tissues, compounds such as polyphenols, flavonoids, and antioxidants that have well-documented health-promoting effects.

To recover these compounds efficiently, we focused on developing and optimizing a cascade extraction process. This method involves a step-by-step application of multiple extraction techniques to the same batch of biomass, allowing for a more complete and selective recovery of bioactive molecules. Compared to traditional single-step methods, cascade extraction enables higher yields

and better preservation of compound integrity, which is crucial when dealing with sensitive phytochemicals.

The cascade process applied to halophyte began with pre-treatment steps such as shredding, washing, and drying of the mature biomass. The extraction sequence typically involved subcritical water extraction and percolation extraction methods used in cascades with in-situ filtration processes for product concentration and water recycling. The Halorefine cascade uses pressurized hot water as a solvent, offering a green alternative to commonly used organic solvents. It is particularly effective in dissolving phenolic compounds and flavonoids, which are known for their antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties. Process cascades are optimized for optimal bioactives yield and the combination of processes proved highly effective in terms of both quantity and quality of the recovered compounds.

During the trials, the optimized cascade consistently demonstrated superior performance, especially in extracting total phenolic content and total flavonoid content. However, higher temperatures

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Pictures of the demonstration-scale multistep cascade extraction equipment. Photograph: Malthe Fredsgaard

risk the degradation of some sensitive compounds, indicating the importance of carefully balancing extraction conditions. The reproducibility of the results was also confirmed through repeated experiments, which yielded very similar profiles in terms of compound concentration and antioxidant activity. This consistency is crucial for future industrial-scale applications where reliability and efficiency are paramount.

The bioactive extracts obtained from *S. ramosissima* were not only abundant but also rich in well-known compounds such as quercetin and isorhamnetin, both of which are associated with strong antioxidant activity, antiviral and potential health benefits. These compounds were confirmed through advanced mass spectrometry techniques and were found in meaningful concentrations. The antioxidant activity of these extracts was tested using established assays and demonstrated strong potential for use in functional animal feed or nutraceutical products. In particular, cascade extraction doubled the antioxidant activity of the extracts, tripled their flavonoid content, and substantially increased overall polyphenol levels.

Beyond the extraction itself, the findings contribute valuable knowledge to the development of green biorefinery concepts, particularly for halophyte-based raw materials. The successful application of cascade extraction to *S. ramosissima* illustrates how process optimization can significantly improve the efficiency and value of bioactive compound recovery. With its robustness, high compound yield, and reproducibility, this method lays the foundation for future commercial use of halophyte-derived ingredients in sustainable aquaculture and other sectors.

The antibacterial capacity of *Salicornia ramosissima* extracts against aquatic pathogens

The *Salicornia ramosissima* extracts developed by AAU and Halorefine A/S showed great potential to be included in aquafeeds due to their interesting profiles in bioactive compounds. Specifically, five extracts derived from different steps of the extraction cascade were produced for subsequent analysis: Extracts 1, 2 and 3, XAD and FERM.

An initial screening phase performed by IGNITION's team at CIIMAR explored the ability of these extracts to kill or inhibit the growth of key pathogenic bacteria commonly affecting farmed aquatic animals, before conducting cell-based or animal experiments. The *in vitro* bactericidal and bacteriostatic activities of *Vibrio anguillarum*, *Vibrio harveyi*, *V. parahaemolyticus*, *Aeromonas hydrophila*, *Yersinia ruckeri*, *Edwardsiella tarda*, ***Photobacterium damsela* subsp. piscicida**, and *Tenacibaculum maritimum* were evaluated. The aim was to determine the extracts' bactericidal activity after a defined exposure period (2.5 hours) and their ability to inhibit bacterial growth over 24 hours. The results quickly revealed the clear potential of all tested extracts, at concentrations ranging from 0.125 mg/mL to 0.5 mg/mL, to kill key aquatic pathogens such as *T. maritimum*, *Photobacterium* spp., *V. anguillarum*, and *A. hydrophila*. Moreover, Extracts 1, 2, and 3, at the highest concentration, demonstrated additional bactericidal activity against *V. parahaemolyticus* and *Y. ruckeri*.

Because bacteria can sometimes recover from an initial bactericidal effect, bacterial growth was monitored over a 24-hour period following

exposure. While most of the extracts exhibited rapid bactericidal effects, their long-term ability to inhibit bacterial regrowth varied. Some extracts maintained growth-inhibitory activity more effectively than others, and susceptibility also varied among bacterial species. Notably, all tested extracts demonstrated the ability to inhibit the long-term growth of key pathogens such as *V. anguillarum*, *V. harveyi*, and *P. damselae* subsp. *piscicida*. In particular, the XAD and Extract 3 stood out, showing both rapid killing effects and sustained inhibition of bacterial growth over time.

Immunomodulatory effects of *Salicornia ramosissima* extracts on fish macrophages

After testing the antibacterial effects of the extracts, CIIMAR's and NORD University's teams joined forces to evaluate the immunomodulatory potential of the bioactives at various doses. This was done using both cell lines and primary cell cultures derived from model fish species, including rainbow trout, European seabass, and Atlantic salmon. Screening was conducted by assessing cellular response, aiming at minimizing cytotoxicity while modulating immune functions. Data from head-kidney primary adherent cells from Atlantic salmon displayed XAD as a strong immune-enhancing extract for its effects on oxidative stress and phagocytosis, both in the presence or absence of a stimulation with fish pathogens.

Moreover, studies on head kidney primary adherent cells from European seabass challenged with inactivated *Tenacibaculum maritimum* suggest that Extract 3 and XAD may exhibit anti-inflammatory properties by modulating

oxidative stress, while FERM appears to act as an immunostimulant. Ongoing work is being performed involving other cellular matrices and more detailed time-course analysis to capture dynamic cellular responses to the extracts at both functional and gene expression levels.

Incorporation of *Salicornia ramosissima* extracts in diets for shrimp and fish

Following the promising *in vitro* results, showcasing the antibacterial and immune-modulating effects of the extracts, Extract 3 and XAD were selected for inclusion in diets used in *in vivo* trials with fish and shrimp. The extracts were added at inclusion levels of 0.1% and/or 0.5% to diets formulated to mimic standard commercial feeds used in the production of each target species. The aim was to assess their potential as functional additives and evaluate their impact on the animals' zootechnical performance, health status, and resistance to stress and disease. To achieve this, fish and shrimp were fed either extract-supplemented diets or an unsupplemented control diet for up to four weeks. Results showed that neither extract, at either tested inclusion level, compromised the growth, feeding efficiency, or survival of whiteleg shrimp. Similarly, no negative effects on these parameters were observed in Atlantic salmon parr when the diets were supplemented with the extracts at the 0.5% inclusion level. These findings confirm that Extract 3 and XAD fulfill the primary requirement for their use as functional additives for these species, namely the absence of adverse effects on these key performance indicators. Samples collected during the trials are currently being analyzed to investigate

Salmon macrophages, isolated from the head kidney, are exposed to halophyte extracts and then incubated with fluorescent bioparticles. The number of macrophages engulfing the particles, as well as the number of particles being engulfed are quantified by imaging flow cytometry. Image: Mariana Ferreira

potential improvements in the animals' overall health condition and to assess the full potential of the extracts as functional additives. Additionally, diets supplemented with the extracts will be tested as both prophylactic and therapeutic strategies against several pathogenic agents, including *Tenacibaculum maritimum*, *Yersinia ruckeri*, and *Vibrio parahaemolyticus*. These initial results justify further investigation into the targeted applications of these extracts under more challenging and disease-prone conditions

Future directions

IGNITION team has successfully identified the most promising *Salicornia ramosissima* extracts for inclusion in aquafeeds. Future work aims to evaluate the dietary incorporation of these extracts in mitigating stress-induced effects and immune response by targeting the stress biomarkers identified in previous work packages of the project. This assessment will be carried out in both shrimp and fish, focusing on improvements in overall health and gut immunity. Animal performance will be evaluated using standard analytical techniques, including enzymatic assays, disease resistance tests, microbiota analysis, RNA sequencing, and proteomics. All collected data will contribute to the development of the disease prediction model. Additionally, the extraction methods of bioactives from *S. ramosissima* will be further refined to expand its application, especially in the scope of aquafeed, reinforcing its role in promoting circular and sustainable practices within the aquaculture bioeconomy.

Closing remarks

In conclusion, *Salicornia ramosissima* has proven to be a highly promising plant for the production of natural bioactive compounds. The cascade extraction approach, particularly the integration of subcritical water extraction with Soxhlet extraction, resulted in significantly improved yields of phenolic and flavonoid compounds. These bioactive compounds have demonstrated *in vitro* immunomodulatory effects on immune cells from different fish species. Ongoing feeding trials with whiteleg shrimp, European seabass, Atlantic salmon and rainbow trout aim to validate these results, with the goal of developing functional diets capable of improving their performance, gut health and disease resistance.

The combined efforts of AAU, Halorefine A/S, CIIMAR, Riasearch and Nord University teams, working within the scope of IGNITION, mark a significant step forward in the sustainable exploitation of halophytes and highlights their potential to be included in aquafeeds to improve the resilience of farmed aquatic animals.

Whiteleg shrimp feed supplemented with Extract 3 used in the *in vivo* trials.
Photograph: André Barreto

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